

THE ADVANTAGES OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE THROUGH ONLINE PLATFORMS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted for the benefits of online educational platforms of teaching English language in higher education institutions as well as the facilities that both teachers and students of higher education institutions can have. And, educational technologies in use will be reviewed.

The world of learning is changing around us as a result of technology's ability to expand educational opportunities. Educational expert Nadim Nsouli says, "I believe that learning through technology will continue to transform teaching practice. It can really help to tackle some of the challenges that are faced in the education sector such as efficiency, workload, accessibility, and inclusion." Education has become more broadly available to everyone thanks to the ability to learn remotely. Children who don't study well in typical school settings can work at their own pace in a secure atmosphere, adults who have a different lifestyle due to illness or travel can enhance their education, and people who work full-time yet want to learn more remotely and on their own time.

A wider range of instructional strategies and resources are available to teachers thanks to new technologies. Mobile educational apps, collaborative platforms, learning analytics, virtual reality, and many more cutting-edge tools and methodologies are a few of these new technologies. The learning process may be made considerably more interesting and engaging for both students and professors in higher education institutions with the aid of these modern educational tools and techniques.

Teachers benefit more from online instruction. The following are some of the main benefits of online education for teachers:

- Individual focus on students
- Ease of connecting with students
- Increased engagement in classes
- Organized methods for checking and grading assignments

Besides, with the help of new modern technologies and AI tools (Artificial Intelligence), teachers are no longer to check the assignments of students. The system will automatically check the assignments and show the results of students. There are more than 10 online English language teaching platforms all over the world. The methods and technics are different. Every learner will choose according to their preferences. The practical one, which is being used widely through many international universities, is video conference. The practical case of this style is that both teachers and students will work in a real time, which allows students to give questions which are difficult to understand of a topic. The other advantages of teaching English language online are as follows:

✓ Work from home:

Many people know that working from home had been just a desire until the pandemic period. The new technologies facilitate it and educators can easily schedule their working hours in a day without any concerns of having to go to the workplaces. This also includes the travelling processes as long as they have enough educational environment around themselves such as silence, stable internet connection and so on.

✓ Educational tools:

Many new modern technologies are widely used in educational sphere nowadays such as PowerPoint Presentations, Video materials, DOC, PDF, EPUB files, other English language related materials and so on. These will serve as a time-saving tools of educators as they have once been saved and uploaded on the platform, students can use unlimitedly.

✓ The cost:

Teaching through online platforms have proven that they save money. Because the premises of higher educational institutions are limited to number of students. But online platforms will not choose time or place, as a consequence of which individuals will not have to build new construction. Students that are far from can benefit of saving their money on apartments and travel.

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